

MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM TASHKILOTINING OTA-ONALAR BILAN O'ZARO MUNOSABAT SHAKLLARI

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada ota-onalar va maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarining o'zaro hamkorlik munosabatlarining yangi usullarini tashkil etish va oila bilan ishlashning turli shakllaridan foydalanishning samarali natijasi haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Tashrif, ochiq eshik kunlari, ekskursiya, kommunikativ sifatlar, hamkorlik, mehnat.

FORMS OF INTERACTION OF THE PRESCHOOL ORGANIZATION WITH PARENTS

Abstract. The article reflects on the effective result of the organization of new methods of interaction of parents and preschool educational organizations and the use of various forms of work with the family.

Key words: visit, open door days, excursion, communicative qualities, cooperation, labor.

ФОРМЫ ВЗАИМОДЕЙСТВИЯ ДОШКОЛЬНОЙ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ С РОДИТЕЛЯМИ

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается эффективный результат организации новых способов взаимодействия родителей и дошкольных образовательных организаций и использования различных форм работы с семьей.

Ключевые слова: визит, дни открытых дверей, экскурсия, коммуникативные качества, сотрудничество, труд.

“Ik qadam” maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari davlat o'quv dasturining majburiy qismi oilani ta'lim va tarbiyaga jalb qilishdir. Ba'zida pedagoglar, shunchaki ota-onalarni yig'ishlarga, tadbirlarga va tantanalarga taklif qilish bilan oilalar ishtiroki ta'minlangan deb o'ylashadi. Biroq olia ishtiroki shunchaki maktabgacha faoliyatda qatnashishdan ko'proq narsani anglatadi. Ota-onalar va maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarining o'zaro hamkorligi kamdan-kam hollarda darhol yuzaga keladi. Bu sabr- toqatni, tanlangan maqsadga qat'iy rioya qilishni va ota-onalar bilan hamkorlik qilishning yangi usullarini doimiy ravishda izlashni talab qiladigan uzoq jarayon, uzoq davom etadigan mashaqqatli mehnatdir. Ota-onalar va tarbiyachilarning o'zaro hamkorligi va bir-biri bilan ma'lumot almashish uchun imkoniyat yaratadigan faoliyatning turli shakllari va usullari mavjud:

- umumiy va guruh ota-onalar yig'ilishlari;
- ota-onalar ishtirokidagi mashg'ulotlar;
- tashrif kunlari;
- ochuq eshik kunlari;
- amaliy mashg'ulotlar;
- birgalikdagi ekskursiyalar;

Oila bilan ishlashning turli shakllaridan foydalanish ota-onalarning maktabgacha tarbiya tashkilotiga bo‘lgan ishonchini uyg‘otishga imkon beradi. Pedagog ish turini rejalashtirayotganda har doim zamonaviy ota-onalar, shuningdek, doimiy izlanish, o‘z-o‘zini rivojlantirish va hamkorlikka tayyor bo‘lgan zamonaviy kishilarning fikrlaridan kelib chiqishi mumkin bo‘lgan o‘ziga xoslik, interaktivlik talablarni tanlashi mumkin.

Guruhli ota-onalar yig‘ilishi - bu tarbiyachilarning ota-onalar jamoasi bilan hamkorlikning ta’sirchan shakli bo‘lib, bolalarni tarbiyalashdagi vazifalari va metodlari bilan tashkiliy tanishish mumkin. Bu ota-onalar bilan hamkorlikning eng samarali shakllaridan bo‘lib ota-onalarning istak-xohishlarini inobatga olish bilan turli xil mavzularda tashkil etiladigan mavzuli ota-onalar yig‘ilishi sanaladi. Masalan, “Mana, biz yana bir yoshga ulg‘aydik” mavzusida tashkillangan yig‘ilishda bolalarning rivojlanishidagi yoshga doir xususiyatlar, tarbiyalashdagi vazifalar, berilgan yosh guruhidagi ta’lim ishlarining o‘ziga xosliklari va bolalarda kommunikativ sifatning rivojlantirilishi usullari yoritiladi. Mashg‘ulotlarga ota-onalarni jalb etishda nutqli o‘yinlarni “Bolalar bilan birga o‘ynaymiz” mavzusida tashkil etish natijasida esa bola nutqi rivojlanishida ota-onaning roli, bolalarda nutqni muvaffaqiyatli rivojlantirishning bir qator omillari yuzaga keladi. Tarbiyachi bunda ota-onalarni mazkur mavzu bo‘yicha bajariladigan ishlarning mazmuni bilan tanishtiradi, ota-onalarga bolada fonematik eshitishni rivojlantirish uchun maxsus o‘yinlar va mashqlar taklif etishi mumkin. Mashg‘ulot jarayonida ota-onalar bolalarning nutqini rivojlantirish va takomillashtirish zaruratiga ishonch hosil qiladilar; nutqli o‘yin turlari bilan tanishadilar hamda uyda o‘z farzandlari bilan shug‘ullanishni o‘rganadilar.

Ochiq eshik kunlari yoki tashrif kunlarini o‘tkazishda “Oilaviy musobaqalar”, “Guruhlarni bezash”, “MMTda obodonlashtirish” ishlari, Aksiyalar tashkil etish kabi tadbirlarni tashkillash tarbiyachi, ota-onalar va bolalarning hamkorligini yanada mustahkamlaydi. Ota-onalar hamkorligidagi mashg‘ulotlarada bolaga ko‘mak, yordam berish, boshqa ota-onalar bilan muloqotga kirishish, bola bilan hamkorlikda harakatlanish yoki muammoga yechim topish bolalar va kattalar o‘rtasidagi munosabatni rivojlantiradi. Ota-ona maqsadli pedagogic ishning muhimligini tushunadi, uning mazmuni va metodologiyasini yaxshi anglaydi va uni uyda, amalda qo‘llashi mumkin bo‘ladi. Dam olish shakllarini tashkillashda birgalikdagi ekskursiyalar maqsadga muvofiq. “Biz tabiatning do‘stlarimiz” mavzusida ekskursiya tashkil etish natijasida ota-onalar o‘z farzandini ichki tomondan boshqa bolalar bilan o‘zaro aloqadorlikdagi fazilatlarini ko‘rish imkoniga ega bo‘ladilar, shu bilan birga tabiatga bo‘lgan e’tibor kuchayadi. Ota-onalarda esa hamkorlikda ishlashdan qoniqish hissi paydo bo‘ladi.

Ayrim ota-onalarning bandligini inobatga olgan holda muloqotning innovatsion ko‘rinishlari “Ota-onalar telegram kanali” va “Ishonch telefoni”, “Ota-onalar bilan onlayn maslahatlashuv” va boshqalar qo‘llaniladi. Ota-onalarda xayrixohlikning uyg‘otilishi, ularning ishonchini qozona bilish, ochiq muloqotga chorchash, pedagog bilan o‘z fikr-mulohazalari, shubhagumonlari bilan o‘rtoqlashish muhimdir. Bularning barchasi bolani yaxshiroq tushinishga, maktabgacha ta’lim tashkilotida va uyda aniq bola shaxsini tarbiyalashning muammolarini hal qilishdagi optimal yechimlarni topishga yordam beradi. MTTning oila bilan o‘zaro munosabati turli yo‘llar bilan amalga oshirilishi mumkin, faqat rasmiyatchilikka yo‘l qo‘ymaslik kerak.

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